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Baseline, Spatial and Temporal Variation of Respirable [PM_{2.5}] Particulate Matter in Isoko Land

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Research Article

Baseline, Spatial and Temporal Variation of Respirable [PM_{2.5}] Particulate Matter in Isoko Land

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ABSTRACT

Airborne particles are the most obvious form of air pollutants in Nigeria; a link is now being established between the low life expectancy in Nigeria and the ubiquitous suspended particulate matter.

This article quantified the baseline, spatial and temporal distributions of PM_{2.5} airborne particles in Isoko land with numerous oil wells and flow stations. It has been established that the health effects of atmospheric particulate matter are related to its ability to permeate the respiratory system. It has been generally recognized that, respiratory defense mechanisms have the ability to retain up to 99 percent of particles larger than 10µm from the inhaled air stream but the smaller particles (2.5µm and less) which are called respirable particles, are highly toxic because of their ability to penetrate deep into the respiratory tract and blood stream where they cause various forms of respiratory and pulmonary diseases.

Airborne particulate matter quantification in this study was accomplished by using a Microdust Pro real time dust monitor (Casella CEL 176000A). Sampling was done for a year in the seventeen (17) sampling sites created in the study area. A baseline PM_{2.5} range of 4 – 310 µg/m³ was measured.

There was uniformity in the distribution of respirable particles (PM_{2.5}) at the sampling sites (ANOVA, P=0.6669, F=0.8156, df 16). The dry season PM_{2.5} values were statistically significantly higher (ANOVA, P= 2.377E-35, F=29.18, df 11) than the wet season levels.

Quite worrisome, is the breach of the National Ambient Air Quality standard (NAAQS) 24 hours PM_{2.5} threshold of 65µg/m³ limit in all the sampling sites and this means that the quality of air breathe in by the people is poor and it is a pointer to quality of life in Isoko land. Violation of this limit is also suggestive of health and environmental concerns. The sources identified to contribute the highest values are vehicular traffic and re-suspended dust due to the condition of the roads and direct farming activities (anthropogenic particles).

Keywords: Respirable particulate matter, baseline, spatial, temporal, cluster.

1. INTRODUCTION

Particulate matter pollution has been widely explored in many parts of the world (A.S. Zakey *et al.*, 2008; S. I. Efe, 2008; E.A. Oluyemi & O.I. Asubiojo 2001). It is very important to know the concentration of particulate matter in the atmosphere since suspended particulate matter pollution has an influence on human health, plants, animals and the environment (M.E. Sufian 2011). Suspended particulate matter is a nearly an ever-present urban pollutant and the most visible. It is a multifaceted combination of small and large particles of varying origin and chemical composition and properties. The health effects of particulate matter are dependent on the size of the particles. Generally, the smaller particulate matters (those with greater surface area) are the more toxic ones. The human respiratory system has a defense mechanism that filters particles with a diameter of 10µm or more when air is inhaled through the nostrils. The bigger particles then to remain in the throat while the smaller ones (PM_{2.5} or PM₁) get into the windpipe and into the lower respiratory system. It has also been established that they are also more toxic since they frequently consist of heavy metals and carcinogenic organic compounds (S. H^ormann, B. Pfeiler & E. Stadlober, 2005).

Respirable particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) can simply be defined as that fraction of Particulate Matter which enters the body and is small enough to pass through all the defense mechanisms in the nose and upper respiratory system and goes deep into the lungs. These particles that infiltrate deep into the respiratory system are generally beyond the body's natural clearance mechanisms of cilia and mucous and are more likely to be retained. Respirable particulate matter is also defined as any airborne particle that has a diameter of less than 10 microns which is capable of penetrating deep into the alveoli.

The median aerodynamic diameter of respirable particulate matter is about 2.5µm and is also the mass fraction of total air borne particles which are taken through nose and mouth with a particle size variation from about 2.5 to 100µm in diameter. It is usually made up of smoke and dust from industrial processes, road traffic,

construction, agriculture, gas flaring, incineration of refuse, heat and power generation, as well as plant pollen and other natural sources (Microsoft Encarta Encyclopedia 2001; Ediagbonya et al. 2012).

Characterization of respirable particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) has shown that they contain a large number of mutagenic and carcinogenic substances. Particulate matter pollution has been traced to cause premature mortality, lung cancer, respiratory and cardiovascular health problems (M. E. Sufian, 2011). Some significant negative effects of Long-term exposure to particulate matter <10 mm in diameter are Lung-function proxy for the development of large (forced expiratory volume in one second) and small (mid expiratory flow between 25 and 75% of the forced vital capacity) airways respectively (F. Horak Jr *et al.*, 2002).

It has been shown that particulates are dangerous because of the role they play in the development of lung cancer and higher rates of mortality (Schwela, 2000).

Gas flaring as one of the sources of particulate matter generation is the careful and regulated burning of natural gases associated with oil exploration. The constant flaring of associated gas has left a destructive effect on the surrounding environment of the Niger Delta Area, where the activities of oil production mainly take place (E.O. Adeniyi, R. Olu-Sule & A. Anyaye, 1983). Nigeria has an average daily crude oil output in excess of two million barrels per day, with over 200 gas-flaring sites. Some of these gas-flaring sites have been on continuously for over 20 years.

About 75% of the 22 billion standard cubic feet (SCF) of associated gas produced daily alongside the crude oil in Nigeria is being flared (Bailey et al., 2000). The volume of gas flared in Nigeria is equivalent to one quarter of the current power consumption of the African continent.

The use of coal for power generation in South Africa and gas flaring in the Niger Delta have been traced to be the main sources of carbon dioxide emissions in Sub-Saharan Africa (south of the Sahara). Gas flaring has also been implicated as a major contributor to the accumulation of green house gases in the atmosphere thereby adding to the climate change pandemonium. Continuation of gas flaring is a direct contradiction of the determined stand taken by nations of the world to fight climate change in practical terms.

For neighbouring communities to gas flares, the toxic mixture of substances produced from gas flares have found to have serious health impacts in the form of respiratory illnesses, asthma, blood disorders, cancer, painful breathing and chronic bronchitis (S. I. Efe, 2006).

A link has also been established between flared gas and acid rains that pollute creeks and streams, damage vegetation and corrode roofs of homes. The acid rain occurs when sulphur and nitrogen oxides mix with moisture in the atmosphere.

The purpose of this work is to look into the activities of flow stations and how they impact air quality in Isoko land and establish a link between air quality and low life expectancy.

This work could also be used as a preliminary study to obtain background information about the level of respirable particulate matter in Isoko land, their spatial and temporal distribution as well as to ascertain the quality of air people breathe in Isoko land.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Study Area

This study was carried out in six different oil-producing communities in Isoko land (North and South local government areas) of Delta state in the south-south geopolitical region of Nigeria. Isoko land is found in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria in West Africa, occupying an area of about 1,200 square kilometres, with a residual population estimate of over 750,000 people by 2006 census.

Isoko Land is among the most densely populated areas in Nigeria, with an average of 300 persons per square kilometre compared with the average of 198 for Delta State and 130 for Nigeria and this has resulted in shortage of farmland, a shortage also caused by oil exploration activities in the region.

Isoko Land is essentially rural with two semi-urban centres and no urban centre. Isoko land lies within the economic shadow of the vibrant industrial and commercial Warri metropolis.

In between these communities are three flow stations namely: Ogini, Uzere and Olomoro. The study area is located within the co-ordinates of latitude N05° 23' 0" - N05° 36' 0" Longitude E006° 8' 0" - E006° 17' 0". The study area has an estimated land mass of 232.56 square kilometers and with a population estimate of 142, 582 people (NPC 2006). Ozoro and Oleh are the semi-urban communities while the remaining four communities are rural. The rural dwellers engage themselves in farming, hunting, rubber tapping and rural intra-transportation due to the accessibility of these communities via paved and unpaved roads. The people also engage in cassava processing, smoking of fishes, and their major way of waste disposal is either by burning or indiscriminate dumping of the waste in the bush. The major means of cooking is through burning of fossil fuel (Fire wood or kerosene). However, as mentioned earlier all these communities are within the proximity of three flow stations where associated gas is being flared on a daily basis. All these afore-mentioned activities are veritable generators of particulate matter in the environment.

Figure 1: Map of Delta State showing Isokoland.

Figure 2: Map of Isoko land reflecting respirable fractions (PM_{2.5}) concentrations (µg/m³) from the various sampling locations.

Table 1: Sampling Sites, description and their Coordinates

S/N	Sampling site	Site code	Co-ordinates
1	Close to Uzere flow station flare tip	SP.UZF	5° 24' 25"N, 6° 10' 22"E
2	Mango tree along Uzere town entrance from Oleh axis	SP.UZE	5° 24' 9"N, 6° 10' 29"E
3	Close to residential houses opposite Uzere Police station	SP.UZT	5° 35' 25"N, 6° 10' 55"E
4	Front residential house opposite Uzere Daily Market	SP.UZM	5° 35' 15"N, 6° 9' 5"E
5	Close to Ogini flow station flare tip	SP.OGF	5° 35' 25"N, 6° 16' 55"E
6	Front residential house in Okpaile Main Town	SP.OKT	5° 35' 24"N, 6° 16' 55"E
7	This site was created in front of the Catholic church in Ellu just beside the market	SP.ELT	5° 34' 18"N, 6° 16' 40"E
8	Front of the Apostolic church, along Ellu/Okpaile road	SP.ELE	5° 34' 43"N, 6° 16' 15"E
9	Front of a residential house Ozoro Entrance Agbaza road Junction	SP.OZE	5° 32' 57"N, 6° 13' 38"E
10	Front of an office building Ala Square by Urude quarters	SP.OZT	5° 30' 28"N, 6° 12' 40"E
11	Ozoro Exit (NDC by Express Junction)	SP.OZX	5° 29' 50"N, 6° 11' 30"E
12	Close to Olomoro flow station flare tip	SP.OLF	5° 25' 42"N, 6° 9' 18"E
13	Olomoro Main Town	SP.OLT	5° 25' 8"N, 6° 8' 48"E
14	Olomoro town entrance (Express road Junction)	SP.OLE	5° 24' 56"N, 6° 8' 36"E
15	Front of a residential house at Oleh Town close to Nyaga Market	SP.LET	5° 27' 8"N, 6° 12' 12"E
16	Bush along Ozoro/Idheze road at Ozoro axis	SP.CT1	5° 29' 14"N, 6° 13' 58"E
17	Bush along Ozoro/Oleh road at Oleh axis	SP.CT2	5° 26' 28"N, 6° 12' 40"E

2.2 Sampling and Experimental Methods

The mass concentrations for PM_{2.5} presented in this paper were monitored by means of Microdust Pro Dust Kit. Precise measurement of respirable airborne particulate matter was carried out through an optical method using the "Microdust pro" monitor (P. Baltrėnas & M. Kvasauskas, 2005).

The Microdust Pro measures particulate concentrations using a near forward angle light scattering technique where Infrared light of 880nm wavelength is projected through the sampling volume. The contact of the projected light with the particles causes the light to scatter. The amount of light scattered is proportional to the mass concentration and this is measured by the photo detector. To minimize the uncertainty associated with particle color, shape and refractive index; a narrow angle of scatter (12- 20°) is used.

Various studies have shown that the monitor "Microdust pro" has the highest level of sensibility for measuring inspirable fractions (particulate matter with a diameter from 0.1 µm to 10 µm).

The Microdust Pro has a Wide measurement range from 0.001 to 2500 mgm⁻³ in single meter, Data-logger with >15,700 readings, Detachable probe, TSP, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} (Respirable) measurements, Firmware calibration and zero in the field, and simultaneous collection of a gravimetric (filtered) sample of the particulate matter. It is a rugged, hand-held, data-logging meter for the real-time detection of airborne particulate matter, fumes and aerosols. By using both the gravimetric and in situ measurement, two averages are collected over the exposure period. One is from the filter, whilst the other is provided by the averaging function within the instrument. It is then possible to derive the difference in these two figures and correct accordingly. Sampling was done for a year in the seventeen (17) sampling sites created in the study area and sampling was for 8 hours per sampling site. This method has been used and proven to be accurate and reliable. (P. Baltrėna & J. Morkuniene, 2006; Ruschioni E. *et al.*, 2011; K. Agne, Jorma Pottala & Virginijus Petronis, 2008; Thatcher T. H. *et al.*, 2005). Total Suspended Particulate matter (TSP) refers to all particles surrounded by air in a given volume of air.

2.3 Results and Discussions

The respirable particulate matter distribution within Isoko land shows that the highest PM_{2.5} levels were observed in the semi-urban areas of Ozoro (119µg/m³), Oleh (94µg/m³), and Uzere (99µg/m³), while the lowest values were recorded in Ellu (81µg/m³) and Okpaile (62µg/m³) the most rural among the various sampling sites. Figure 3 shows the mean concentration (µg/m³) distribution across the various sampling sites.

There was uniformity in the distribution of respirable particles PM_{2.5} at the sampling sites (ANOVA, P=0.6669, F=0.8156, df 16), however the dry season PM_{2.5} values were statistically significantly higher (ANOVA, P= 2.377E-35, F=29.18, df 11) than the wet season levels.

Cluster analysis separated the data into two groups. Analysis of similarity (ANOSIM) showed that the groups are separated (R=0.6667, P=0.0004). It also separated the dry season (Dec-Apr 2012) from the rainy season (May-Nov). ANOSIM (R=0.88, P=0.0015) which shows that the groups are clearly separated. Figure 4

shows the anosim box plot of the seasonal variation of PM_{2.5} while Figure 5 shows the anosim box plot their spatial variation. Figure 6 is the dendrogram that clearly show the separation of the PM_{2.5} into two groups.

The sources identified to contribute the highest values are vehicular traffic and re-suspended dust due to the condition of the roads and direct farming activities (anthropogenic particles).

Figure 3: Mean distribution of Respirable [PM_{2.5}] particulate Matter in Isoko Land

Table 2: Comparison of Respirable Particulate Matter results of this study with others.

S/N	Site /location	Range/Mean (µg/m ³)	References
1	Isoko Area	33.50 – 92.83	Current Study
2	Urban/Sapele	104.17 – 331.44	Ediagbonya (2012)
3	Rural/Obaretin	104.17 – 208.33	Ediagbonya (2012)
4	London/UK	39	Adams et al (2001)
5	Urban/Ile-Ife	11 – 238	I.B. Obioh et al (2005)
6	Urban/Seoul	86.9	Yon Shin Kim et al (2002)
7	Urban/China	106 – 145	L.Y. Chan et al (2002)
8	Urban/Belgrade	61	M. Tabic et al (2006)
9	Urban/Milan	66(W) 43(S)	Maroazzan et al (2003)
10	Urban/Madrid	34	E. Manoli et al (2002)
11	Urban/Berlin	30	X. Querol et al (2001)
12	Urban/Mumbai/India	35 – 115.85	P. Kothai et al (2008)
13	Guatemalan/Finland	140 – 1,210	Smith K.R. et al (1993)

Figure 4: Seasonal anosim box plot of respirable particulate matter in Isoko land

Figure 5: Spatial anosim box plot of respirable particulate matter in Isoko land

Figure 6. Dendrogram of respirable particulate matter in Isoko land.

The $PM_{2.5}$ values obtained in this research compared well with other similar research work that have been carried out in some parts of Nigeria (I. B. Obioh, F. S. Olise, O. K. Owoadi & H. B. Olaniyi, 2005; Edigbonya et al., 2013) and also they compared well with those obtained from some advanced countries such as the UK, China, Germany, Korea and India as evident in table 2 above.

3 CONCLUSION

This study has shown that, though Isoko land is rural; there is a gradual increase in the concentration of respirable $PM_{2.5}$ particulate matter; this is obvious from the monthly mean of $91\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, which is 40% higher than $65\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ NAAQS threshold.

The semi-urban towns of Ozoro, Oleh and Uzere were more polluted than the other rural communities. There was also a significant variation in the level of $PM_{2.5}$ particulates in the semi-urban sampling locations of Isoko land. From the source apportionment, it was observed that flow station activities do not directly impair the air quality of Isoko area.

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